

THEORETICAL RESEARCH OF METHODS FOR STUDYING AND ANALYZING DEVELOPMENT RISKS

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Abstract. *This article explores the legal foundations for organizing occupational safety in industrial settings and highlights specific methods used to analyze the levels of risk arising under various working conditions. It presents effective techniques for hazard analysis, including the “What if...?” approach and “Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA),” offering recommendations based on predictive mechanisms.*

Keywords: *occupational safety, legislation, state policy, hazard analysis, technical regulations, risk, risk assessment, hazardous production.*

Introduction. Currently, the effective Law "On Occupational Safety" consists of 36 articles, in which the responsibilities of employers and employees regarding compliance with safety requirements are significantly reinforced. It outlines tasks aimed at ensuring control over the creation of appropriate working conditions and occupational safety measures [1].

One of the key directions of the state's occupational safety policy is the prioritization of employees' life and health, which is established as a fundamental principle. This reflects the law's human-centered approach and its commitment to safeguarding individual interests. State programs in the field of occupational safety are developed and implemented accordingly. The activities of state and economic management bodies, as well as local government authorities, are coordinated in the sphere of occupational safety [1].

Research methods. The development and implementation of safety technologies, techniques, and tools aimed at protecting workers are encouraged. Advances in science and technology, as well as progressive national and international practices in occupational safety, are utilized in this process. Employees who suffer from workplace accidents or occupational diseases are provided with social protection. Consistent international cooperation is also carried out in this area [1,2].

Analyses reveal that one of the main causes of occupational accidents in enterprises is the failure of workers to comply with occupational safety requirements and safety regulations. In some cases, employers also violate safety rules when assigning work hours, scheduling rest periods, or organizing business trips for their employees [1].

To eliminate such violations, the law increases the responsibilities of both employers and employees to comply with occupational safety regulations. It defines their respective rights and obligations. Every worker has the right to a safe and healthy working environment. Employees must be informed by the employer about their working conditions, including the risk of occupational and other diseases, related entitlements and compensations, as well as the types of individual and collective protective equipment provided. Workers are mandatorily covered by state

social insurance against workplace accidents and occupational diseases in accordance with legal procedures. They also undergo unscheduled medical examinations based on medical recommendations, during which their workplace (position) and salary are preserved.

Currently, occupational safety services are being established in organizations. In every organization engaged in production activities with 50 or more employees, an occupational safety service is required to ensure compliance with occupational safety standards and to monitor their implementation. Alternatively, a position must be introduced for a specialist with relevant training in occupational safety. Similarly, in organizations operating 50 or more vehicles, a road traffic safety service must be established, or a road safety specialist must be appointed.

Ensuring occupational safety and workplace health, creating safe and environmentally friendly working conditions, certifying workplaces based on the potential for injury from tools and equipment, conducting regular and periodic medical checkups for employees, and strengthening public oversight of occupational safety remain among the key priorities for all employers and trade unions.

The study and assessment of hazardous factors affecting production activities are carried out based on the "Methodological Guidelines for the Analysis of Hazard Levels at Hazardous Production Facilities" [3].

The hazard analysis process includes the following key stages:

- planning and organizing the work;
- identifying hazards and risks;
- assessing the level of risk;
- developing recommendations for risk mitigation.

To ensure the quality of hazard analysis, it is essential to apply knowledge about the patterns of occurrence and progression of accidents at hazardous production facilities. If results of previous hazard analyses exist for similar hazardous facilities or technical equipment used at such sites, they may be utilized as preliminary reference data. However, in doing so, it must be clearly demonstrated that the facilities and processes are indeed comparable, and that any existing differences do not significantly affect the validity of the analysis outcomes [3].

The objectives and tasks of hazard analysis may vary and should be specified depending on the different stages of the hazardous industrial operation being examined.

a) At the stage of locating a hazardous *production facility (substantiating investments or conducting pre-project work)* or during the design phase, the objectives of hazard analysis generally include the following:

- identifying potential hazards and quantitatively conducting an a priori risk assessment by considering the impact of damaging accident factors on personnel, the population, and the environment;
- analyzing the feasibility of proposed decisions and ensuring that the results are taken into account when selecting the optimal placement of the hazardous production facility, the technical equipment to be used, and the buildings and structures of the facility, taking into consideration the characteristics of the location, proximity to other sites, and economic efficiency;
- providing data for the development of safety instructions, technological regulations, and emergency localization plans for accidents that may occur at hazardous production facilities;
- evaluating alternative proposals related to the siting of the hazardous facility or technical solutions.

b) At the stage of *commissioning (or decommissioning)* a hazardous production facility, the purpose of hazard analysis may include the following:

- identifying hazards and assessing the potential consequences of accidents, as well as clarifying the risk assessments made during earlier operational stages of the hazardous production facility;

- verifying whether the operational conditions comply with industrial safety requirements;
- developing and refining guidelines for *commissioning (or decommissioning)* the facility.

c) At the stage of operation or reconstruction of a hazardous production facility, the objectives of hazard analysis may include:

- verifying compliance of operational conditions with industrial safety requirements;
- clarifying information on major hazards (including for the purposes of industrial safety declaration);

- developing recommendations for organizing the activities of supervisory authorities;
- improving operational and maintenance manuals, as well as plans for accident localization at the hazardous production facility;

- evaluating the effectiveness of changes in organizational structures, practical work methods, and maintenance processes in relation to the improvement of the industrial safety management system.

A Brief Description of Key Methods Used in Hazard Analysis of the Labor Process [3,5,6].

“What if...?” Method. This method belongs to the group of qualitative risk assessment techniques based on examining whether the operating conditions or the project comply with industrial safety requirements.

The questions and answers regarding the compliance of a hazardous production facility with industrial safety standards, as well as the related recommendations, form the outcome of the checklist. The checklist in the “What if...?” method differs by providing more detailed preliminary data and results concerning the consequences of safety rule violations [6,7].

Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA). This method is used for the qualitative analysis of the risk associated with the technical system under review.

A key feature of this method is that each device (equipment, unit, item) or system (element) is examined based on how it might fail (failure mode and cause) and how this failure might affect the technical system.

In Table 1, the following categories of criteria are applied: By severity of consequences:

- Catastrophic failure – leads to fatalities, serious damage to property, or irreversible environmental harm.

- Critical (non-critical) failure – poses (or does not pose) a threat to human life; causes (or does not cause) significant harm to property or the environment.

- Minor failure – does not belong to any of the above three categories in terms of consequence.

By failure category (criticality):

- A – quantitative risk analysis is mandatory, or special safety measures are required;
- B – quantitative risk analysis is advisable, or specific safety measures should be adopted;
- C – qualitative risk analysis is recommended, or some safety measures should be considered;

- D – no analysis or special (additional) safety measures are required.

This method is applied to analyze complex technical system designs or technical solutions. It is typically conducted over several days or weeks by a team of 3 to 7 experts from various specialties.

Table 1

"Probability of occurrence - severity of consequences" matrix

Frequency of occurrence of the disorder		The severity of the consequences of the violation			
		catastrophic failure	critical breakdown	noncritical breakdown	a violation with minor consequences
A frequent disorder	> 1	A	A	A	C
Maybe a breakdown	$1 - 10^{-2}$	A	A	B	C
Possible disruption	$10^{-2} - 10^{-4}$	A	B	B	C
A rare disorder	$10^{-4} - 10^{-6}$	A	B	C	D
A violation that is unlikely to occur	$< 10^{-6}$	B	C	C	D

Quantitative risk analysis methods are usually carried out by calculating several risk indicators and may include one or more of the methods mentioned above (or use their results) [4,8]. Conducting a quantitative analysis requires highly qualified performers, large volumes of data on equipment failure rates and reliability, expert evaluations, consideration of environmental specifics, weather conditions, the duration of human presence in hazardous areas, and other factors [4,9,10].

Quantitative risk analysis allows for evaluating and comparing various hazards using unified indicators. This method proves to be highly effective in the following cases:

- at the design and siting stage of a hazardous production facility;
- in the justification and optimization of safety measures;
- in assessing the risk of major accidents at hazardous production facilities equipped with similar technical devices (e.g., main pipeline systems);
- in the comprehensive assessment of risks related to accidents affecting humans, property, and the environment.

6. Recommendations for selecting risk analysis methods for different types of activities and operational stages of hazardous production facilities are provided below (see Table 2).

The following designations are used in Table 2:

- “0” — least applicable analysis method;
- “+” — recommended method;
- “++” — most appropriate method.

The methods can be applied individually or in combination with one another. For example, qualitative analysis methods may include quantitative risk criteria (primarily based on expert evaluations, such as using a “probability–severity of consequences” matrix). In full-scale

quantitative risk analysis, the results of qualitative risk analysis should be used as extensively as possible.

Table 2

Recommendations on the choice of methods of risk analysis

Method	Type of activity				
	Placement (pre-project work)	Design	Commissioning/d ecommissioning	Usage	Reconstr uction
"What if..." analysis	0	+	++	++	+
Checklist method	0	+	+	++	+
Hazard and feasibility analysis	0	++	+	+	++
Fault types and consequences analysis	0	++	+	+	++
Fault and event tree analysis	0	++	+	+	++
Quantitative risk analysis	++	++	0	+	++

Comprehensive assessment of accident risks is based on analyzing the causes of accidents (such as equipment failure, human error, or external influences), the conditions under which they develop, the potential harm to production personnel and the population, as well as the damage to the operating organization's property, third parties, and the environment. The term "risk level" is used to emphasize that we are dealing with a measurable quantity.

At a hazardous production facility, where the operation involves numerous risks, the level of accident risk is determined based on relevant risk indicators. In general, risk indicators are expressed as a combination of the probability (or frequency) and the severity of the potential consequences of the considered undesirable events.

Conclusion. Based on the above-mentioned hazard analysis methods, the following recommendations can be made to reduce hazardous factors in production and to ensure the protection of workers' labor:

1. Special attention should be given to ensuring occupational safety and health, creating safe and environmentally friendly working conditions for employees, and certifying workplaces regarding the risk of injury from tools and equipment.

2. Organizational, technical, and sanitary-hygienic measures should be developed in enterprises and organizations to increase labor productivity and prevent workplace accidents and occupational diseases.

3. The occupational safety management system should be further improved and implemented effectively, including the establishment of a professional risk assessment system.

4. A comprehensive risk indicator reflecting the distribution of risk across the facility and surrounding areas should be used to account for **potential territorial hazards**.

REFERENCES

1. New edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Labor Protection”. September 22, 2016
2. “On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 //“Xalq Sozi” newspaper dated February 8, 2017 No. 28 (6722).
3. Methodological guidelines for analyzing the level of danger at hazardous production facilities. Order of the Head of the State Inspectorate “SANOATKONTEHNAZORAT” No. 158 of 2009.
4. Narziev S. et al. Theoretical analysis of the causes of injury in sports activities and their reduction measures //Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems. – 2020. – T. 12. – №. S2. – C. 166-170.
5. Shovkiddin N. et al. Problems Of Ensuring The Safety Of Sports Activities And Reducing Injuries //Journal of Critical Reviews. – 2020. – T. 7. – №. 11. – C. 428-432.
6. Sulaymonovich S. S., Murtozayevich N. S. Studying and accounting sports injuries //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – №. 7. – C. 759-763.
7. Shovqiddin N. et al. Prevention Of Sport Injuries //Solid State Technology. – 2020. – T. 63. – №. 6. – C. 11868-11875.
8. Shovkiddin Narziev, Sunnatilla Sulaimanov. To the investigation of the tension of the inter-cracked ligaments knee joint //International Journal of Research Available at <https://www.ijournalofresearch.com>: Volume 06 Issue 01 January 2019. 731-735 page.
9. Sulaimanovich S. S., Murtozaevich H. S. Causes and Prevention of Athlete Injuries During Training Sessions and Competitions //JournalNX. – C. 325-329.
10. Murtozaevich N. S., Pirmkulovich B. Z., Safarovich M. B. Radiation Situation Assessment And Safety Measures //JournalNX. – C. 320-324.